

ISSN 0975-4067

KIRANĀVALĪ

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

The New Trivandrum Sanskrit Series
Vol.XVI.Book.I-IV

January - December 2024

किरणावली
Sanskrit Research Foundation
Thiruvananthapuram

ISSN 0975-4067

KIRANĀVALĪ

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

The New Trivandrum Sanskrit Series

Vol.XVI. Book. I-IV

January-December

2024

Sanskrit Research Foundation

T.C 39/37

Thiruvananthapuram-36

KIRANĀVALĪ

ISSN 0975-4067

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14942168>

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

A Peer-Reviewed Research Journal

Editor

Prof. Dr.M. Manimohan (Rtd)

Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

dr.m.manimohan@gmail.com

Executive Editor

Prof. Dr.C.S.Sasikumar (Rtd.)

Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

dr.sasikumarcs@gmail.com

Managing Editor

Prof. Dr.G.Narayanan

Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

dr.g.narayanan@gmail.com

Editorial board

Dr.V.Sisupalapanikkar, Professor of Sanskrit(Rtd.) Uty. of Kerala

Dr.K.Muthulakshmi, Professor of Vedanta, S.S.U.S. Kalady

Dr.R.Vijayakumar, Professor of Vyakarana(Rtd.), S.S.U.S.Kalady

Dr.P.Chithambaran, Professor of Vedanta (Rtd),S.S.U.S. Kalady

Dr.P.K.Dharmarajan, Professor of Sahitya, (Rtd) S.S.U.S. Kalady

Dr.K.K.Sundaresan, Associate Professor in Vedanta, SSUS.Kalady

Dr.S.Sobhana, Professor of Vedanta (Rtd), S.S.U.S.Kalady

Dr.T.Devarajan, Professor of Sanskrit (Rtd), University of Kerala

Associate Editor

Dr.R.Jinu

Associate Professor, Dept of English,

Noorul Islam Centre For Higher Education, Kumaracoil,

Thuckalay, Kanyakumari, Tamil Nadu

jichelnu@gmail.com

Contents

Editors Note		5
Fractions or kalāsavarṇa - Concepts in the Gaṇitasārasaṅgraha (G.S.S) of Mahāvīra	Dr. P.M.Mini	7
Vrikshayurveda Literature- A Review	Dr. K.Murali	12
Existence Of Mind and its Function: Śrī Śankara's Perspective	Dr. V Vasanthakumari	23
Regional Peculiarities in Prakriyāsarvasva	Yamuna.K	30
Parāstotra - Edition and Study	Dr. J.P. Prajith	37
Alienation through Exile: A Critical Introspection into John Dos Passos' Nineteen Nineteen	Dr. Sanil T. Sunny	44
The Evolution of Indian Sculptural Art: Interaction with Western Styles and Development of Modernism	Dr. T.G Jyothilal	49
Scope of Sanskrit Studies in the Kerala Context	Dr.Shylaja S	55
Desamangalam Srikantha Variar - A Versatile Scholar	Dr.V.P.Udayakumar	67
A Comprehensive Review of Adharaneeya and Dharaneeya Vega		
Dr. H.A.Anu, Dr. Haritha Chandran, Dr. Haroon Irshad, Dr. Leena P.Nair		72
A Significant Emphasis on Charakokta Chaturvidha Pariksha		
Dr.Kesavan.V G, Dr.Haroon Irshad, Dr.Leena P.Nair, Dr. Haritha Chandran		84
Concept Of Manas- A Glimpse from Yoga Darsana		
Dr. Anu Gopal, Dr. Haritha Chandran, Dr. Leena P Nair, Dr. Haroon Irshad		96
Women Life in Royal Harem- A Study Based on Nāṭyaśāstra And Mālavikāgnimitra	Dr. Ajitha T S	106
Effective Strategies For Implementing The Integrated Teacher Education Programme Under NEP- 2020	Prof. K.K. Harshkumar, Dr. Anand Rautmale	113
“Pancha Mahabhuta in Ayurveda: Understanding and Practical Applications”		
Dr. Aswiny Sreekumar.T, Dr. Haroon Irshad, Dr. Leena P Nair,		
Dr. C.Ushakumari		121
“Dynamic Portrayals of Women in Amarushatak: Unravelling Love, Creation, Destruction, Submission, and Dominance”	Dr. Preeti R. Pujara	135
Literary Representation of the Ashtamudi Lake sketched through Poetic Imagery: An Exploration based on Selected Poems in Malayalam	Jayalekshmi J	145
Reviving Classical Narratives: Exploring the Cultural, Linguistic, and Literary Significance of Sanskrit Literature in Contemporary Contexts	Dr. Yeshpal,	155
Vedic Thought on Nakshatra Science	Dr. Kanta	172
Vedāntic Reflections in Kālidāsa's Literature: A Journey through Ancient Wisdom	Dr. K. K. Abdul Majeed	179
The Transformative Power of Yogic Meditation: Insights from the Isha Upanishad	Dev Prakash Gujela , Neha Gujela	188
Sanskrit: The Language of Innovation in Ancient Indian Knowledge Systems.	Abdul Rasheed K.	197
The Role of Vedānta as a Mediator between Science and Religion		
Dr. Abdulla Sha R., Dr. Midhun P.,		207
Concept of Guṇa in Bhagavad Gīta	Dr. Shyji K.K.	212

Pancatantram's perspective of accepting an 'hors de combat'	Kasthuri P. K.	217
Integral Yoga of Sri Aurobindo	Remya.S	223
The Historical Aspects Of 'Translation' (Anuvādam) - An Overview	Dr. Sajeesh C S	227
The Malayali Diaspora in the US: A close reading of Mira Jacob	Nirupama Suneetha	235
From Elancon To Kollam: The Transformation of A Port City	Gowri S Panicker	242
Influence of Nārayanīya on Kṛṣṇagīti	Dr Jayanisha K	255
Subverting Ableist Binaries: An Analysis of the Confluence of Disability Studies and Blue Humanities in Toni Crowther's From Wheelchair to Water	Sneha Jacob	263
Connecting the Concept of 'Avatar' to the Concept of Consciousness in Upanishads	Venugopalan P.M	269
Extraction of historicity from Sanskrit literature	Soorya A.P	281
चित्सुखेन प्रतिपादितं अविद्यालक्षणम्	डॉ. सन्तोष सि. आर्	285
सामाजिकसमस्यापरिहारे भरतीयज्ञानपरम्परान्तर्गतस्य योगशास्त्रस्य स्थानम्	डा. श्रीजित् टि.जि	289
पतञ्जलिकालीनः लोकव्यवहारः-महाभाष्याधारेण एकमनुशीलनम्	डा.रूपा, वि	293
मानवीयमूल्यबोधोत्तरणे मृच्छकटिकम्	ड. मृत्युञ्जयमण्डलः परेशकैवर्त्यः	299
रघुवंशमहाकाव्ये रसतत्त्वसमीक्षणम्	काञ्चनवारिकः	304
नारीचैतन्योद्बोधे शङ्खनादः	डॉ टुम्पा जाना	308
आधुनिकसंस्कृतसाहित्ये गलज्जलिकायाः वैशिष्ट्यम्	सतीश चन्द्र दास	313
श्रीमच्छंकराचार्यकृतछान्दोग्योपनिषद्भाष्यस्य कतिपयशब्दवाक्यानां रूपवाक्यशब्दार्थतत्त्वनिरूपणम्	रणिता घोष	321
सदाचारो वेदाश्च ।	डा.अशोक कुमार् एन्.के.	327
साम्प्रतिकसन्दर्भे अपरिग्रहः	डॉ. शुभमयपाहाडी	331
मनुसंहिता : 'ब्रह्मतत्त्व' विषयकम् एकं संक्षिप्तं मतम्	अमल कुमार कर	335
श्रीकाशीमठाधीशानां श्रीमत्सुधीन्द्रतीर्थानां स्तोत्रेषु छन्दांसि तथा सौन्दर्यम्	दिव्यश्री जगदीश पै बि. , & भास्कर वि भट्टः	339
सिद्धान्तग्रन्थेषु ब्राह्मणानाम्	डा. राघवेन्द्रः	347
एतत्संज्ञेत्यल कः समासः	डा. गोपालकृष्णन् रघुः	352
मेघदूतस्य सांस्कृतिकमीमांसा	डा. सत्येन्दु शर्मा	356
जान्-म्यूर-प्रणीतस्य 'श्रीपौलचरितम्' इति महाकाव्यस्य संस्कृतालङ्कारशास्त्रदृष्ट्या समीक्षामिका विमृष्टिः	डा. सौम्यजित् सेनः	360
आधुनिकयुगे संस्कृतशिक्षा प्रसारार्थं विद्यासागरस्यावदानम्	डः तानिया-सिकदारः	369
तद्धितप्रत्ययेषु इत्संज्ञकवर्णाः ।	आतिरा. जि	372
अद्वैतसिद्धेः मङ्गलश्लोकस्य अप्रामाण्यशङ्कावारणम्	कार्तिक शर्मा के , ड. हरिकृष्ण शर्मा के.एन्	376
न्यायव्याकरणतन्त्रानुरोधे पदस्वरूपविवेचनम्	प्रणवेशः भट्टाचार्यः	381
पीयूषवर्षश्रीजयदेवाचार्य-श्रीकेशवमिश्रयोः मते शान्तरसविमर्शः	सत्येनशीटः	387
आलंकारिकदण्डिस्वीकृतः शब्दालङ्कारप्रपञ्चः	डॉ. शुभ्रजित् सेनः	393
लिधा एव पदशब्दस्य प्रवृत्तिः	डा. सुदीप-मण्डलः	400
About the journal		407

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14934683>

“Pancha Mahabhuta in Ayurveda: Understanding and Practical Applications”

Dr. Aswiny Sreekumar.T¹

Dr. Haroon Irshad², Dr. Leena P Nair³, Dr. C.Ushakumari⁴

Abstract

The concept of Pancha mahabhuta principle is widely accepted in Ayurveda. All the available dravyas can be used as medicine but it requires proper logic and reasoning, also this is possible only after deep understanding of pancha mahabhutas as it forms the foundation base of all other siddhantas. In Ashtanga Hridaya it is mentioned that “इति भूतमयो देहः” (Ah.Sh 3/8). Human body is Panchabhautika and the food we eat is also Panchabhautika. (Cha su 26/10). Symmetrical properties of Mahabhutas gives nutrition to corresponding symmetrical organs of body. Susrutacharya has mentioned as Pancha mahabhutas are the supreme power. Without the involvement of them the treatment is not possible (Su.Sha.1/13). Though, Ayurveda is having similar views with Darshana shastras like Vaisheshika, Sankhya etc. in many aspects, but the concept of Pancha mahabhuta in Ayurveda is moulded in such a way that, it becomes helpful in Nidana and Chikitsa, thereby fulfilling its aim of dhatusamya.

1. Dr. Aswiny Sreekumar. T, PG scholar, epartment of Samhita, Siddhanta and Sanskrit, Amrita School of Ayurveda
2. Associate Professor, Department of Maulika Siddhanta (Basic Principles of Ayurveda), Amrita School of Ayurveda, Amrita Vishwa Vidyapeetham, Amritapuri, India.
3. Associate Professor, Department of Maulika Siddhanta (Basic Principles of Ayurveda), Amrita School of Ayurveda, Amrita Vishwa Vidyapeetham, Amritapuri, India.
4. Professor, Department of Maulika Siddhanta (Basic Principles of Ayurveda), Amrita School of Ayurveda, Amrita Vishwa Vidyapeetham, Amritapuri, India.

Introduction

The two fold objectives of Ayurveda is स्वस्थस्य स्वास्थ्य रक्षणं, अतुरस्य विकारप्रशमनम् could only achieved by knowing the structural and functional aspects of living beings. The panchaboutika theory was found most suitable for this purpose and hence is applied in all possible ways so much. So that it became one of the most important basic concept of Ayurveda.

Among the fourfold classification of siddhanta explained by Charaka ,in vimanasthana 8th chapter Pancha mahabhuta Siddhanta can be taken as an example for sarvatatantra siddhanta as it is an undisputed and unanimously accepted doctrine of Indian philosophies propounded after prolong clinical observations. The pancha mahabhuta revolves around the normal functioning of the body, (physiological) , pathological and action of drug in various part of the body(pharmacokinetics).

Etymology

- The word ‘भूत’ means ‘भू सत्तायाम्’ (one that exists)
- महन्ति भूतानि इति महाभूतानि । they are called महाभूत after attaining grossness

When we have reason to believe that something is existent and yet we can not ordinarily perceive it, the term bhuta is used to confirm that it is existent . when there is no shade of doubt in existence we do not ordinarily call the thing bhuta. Though the gross existence are considered to be larger than the primary existence they also can not be perceived with our eyes as they are also very minute. They combine again and again to be seen with naked eyes

Evolution of Pancha Mahabhuta

The two different concepts of evolution of Pancha mahabhuta namely, the evolution of Pancha mahabhuta from their respective tanmatras as akasha mahabhuta from sabda tanmatra and so on with the rest of the mahabhutas. The second concept is evolution of mahabhutas one from the other, as vayu from akasha. Agni from vayu and the rest follow the same order.

The former concept of evolution happened during the parinama krama of moola prakriti(loka srishti),in other words during the creation of the universe.

The second concept of evolution happens during the process of

deha prakriti parinama krama that is during the intra uterine life. This is an on going phenomenon

2

Two Main Processes in the Evolution of Pancha Mahabhutas

1. Uttarothara anupravesha / Bhutantaranupravesha

तेषामेकगुणः पूर्वो गुणवृद्धिः परे परे ।

पूर्वः पूर्वगुणश्चैव क्रमशो गुणिषु स्मृतः ॥(cha sa.1/28)
 आकाश पवन दहन तोय भूमिषु यदा संख्यमेकोत्तर
 परिवृद्धाः...संसर्गात् द्विधा षोडा विभज्यते ॥ (Su.Su. 42/3)

2. Anyonyanupravesha

अन्योऽन्यानुप्रविष्टानि सर्वाण्येतानि निर्दिशेत्
 स्वे स्वे द्रव्ये तु सर्वेषां व्यक्तं लक्षणमिष्यते su sa1/२१॥

The entire maha bhuta theory is mainly based on two major processes. The first one is “*yadasankhyam ekothara parivridhaha*” of gunas during the evolution of mahabhutas one from the other and second one is their integration while entering/forming *pithara* known as *anyonanu pravesha*.

The order of *mahabhutas* mentioned above is important because, starting with *akasha*, the number of attributes per *mahabhuta* increases in the above order. This increase in number of attributes is cumulative, i.e., the attribute of the preceding *mahabhutas* is added to the succeeding one. This process of *gunantara vridhhi* in *mahabhutas* is also known as *bhutantaranupravesha*

Sankaracharya has putforth the theory of Pancheekaranam-one sukshma bhuta gets divided in to two equal parts, one half of it becomes four equal parts of the other four bhutas. Thus ½ of each bhuta gets 1/8th part of the each of the other 4 sukshma bhutas. all the bhutas attain sthoola form through this process

Acharya Susruta has explained reason behind this as because of the mutual combination, mutual help, and mutual admixture, there is presence of all the bhutas in all substances and this is to be inferred by either more or less qualities of bhutas.

Attributes of Mahabhuta

Maha Bhuta	Inherent Gunas	Acquired Gunas				Special Guna
Akasha	Sabda					Aprathighatha
Vayu	Sparsa	Sabda				Chalatva
Agni	Rupa	Sparsa	Sabda			Ushnatwa

Jala	Rasa	Rupa	Sparsa	Sabda		Dravatva
Prithvi	Gandha	Rasa	Rupa	Sparsa	Sabda	Kharatva

The Pancha Mahabhuthas

Mahabhuta	Guna	Origin	Properties
Prithvi	Tamobahula	Jala	Rupa rasa Gandha sparsha
Jala	Satva tamobahula	Agni	Rupa rasa Sparsha drava snigdha
Agni	Teja Bahula	Vayu	Rupa Sparsha
Vayu	Rajobahula	Akasha	Apakaja, anushna sheeta Sparsha
akasha	Satva bahula	Atma	Vibhu, mahat

Applied Aspects Of Pancha Mahabhuta In Ayurveda

The application of pancha mahabhuta Siddhanta can be categorized to four main headings.

- Physiological Aspect
- Pharmacological Aspect
- Clinical Aspect
- Research Aspect

Physiological Aspect

Considering the physiological aspects, from garbha utpatti to marana of a person, Pancha mahabhuta plays a vital role. They are as follows;

- Garbha Utpatti
- Shad Dhatu Purusha
- Prakriti
- Bhutagni
- Panchatwam Gatam

Pancha Mahabhuta in Garbhotpatti

Mahabhuta play basic functions during both formation & development of Garbha. The amalgam of sukra and sonita when embedded in uterus along with Chetana, the Vayu Mahabhuta starts division in embryo to form dosha and avayavas, Teja mahabhuta helps in biotransformation or provides energy, Jala mahabhuta

provides kledan (moisture), Prithvi mahabhuta provides strength by consolidation and Akash mahabhuta helps in overall embryonic growth by creating hollow structures of organs.

Bhuta	Action on Garbha
Vayu	Cell division /multiplication (vibhajana)
Agni	Metabolism (pachana)
Jala	Moistens (kledana)
Prithvi	Compactness (samhanana)
Akasa	Enlargement of size (vivardhana)

Acharya Dalhana clarifying the above verse says that only because of Chetana the Garbha remains alive up to the time of Prasavakala (delivery), in absence of this it gets Kuthita (putrefied) or Vishna (degenerated).

The division of Dosa, Dhatu, Mala, Anga and Pratyanga (major and minor body parts) is done by Vayu.

The Teja by its function of Pachana (metabolism) changes the Rupa (shape), provides general appearance like human structure etc. along with specific features and complexion.

Kledana is done by Jala or in other words the dryness or absorption caused by Vibhaga (division) and Parinama (metabolism) being done by Vayu and Teja respectively is normalized by moistening action of Jala.

The Prithvi perform Samhanana (hardness) or gives shape to Garbha already moistened by Jala. The Vivardhana (enlargement) is done by Akasha by providing space with Adhmapana to the Srotas running all around the body i.e. in Urdhva, Adhah and Tiryak directions, which are created by Vidarana (splitting or division) done by Vayu and Agni

Role Of Mahabhuta in Complexion of Foetus

In the third month of pregnancy, following body constituents are formed and relative functions begin from mahabhuta

Complexion	Susruta	Charaka	Vagbhata
Gaura	Teja+Jala	Teja+Jala+ Akasha	Teja+Jala+Akasha

Krishna	Teja + Prithvi	Teja+Prithvi+ Akasha	Teja+ Prithvi+ Akasha
Shyama	-	All Bhootas Equal	All Bhootas Equal
Gaura Shyama	Teja+Jala+ Akasha	-	-
Krishna Shyama	Teja + Prithvi+ Akasha	-	-
Pingala	-	-	-

Pancha Mahabhuta & Prakriti

Based on predominance of mahabhutas Susruta acharya classified the body constitution into 5 types they are called bhoutika prakriti. (su sa 4/79)

1. Parthiva prakriti
2. Apya prakriti
3. Taijasa prakriti
4. Vaayaveeya prakriti
5. Akasheeya prakriti

According to Acharya Charaka, the mahabhuta vikara prakriti is one among factors that influence the garbha sharira. (Cha vi 8/95)

Pancha Mahabhuta in Digestion

Ushma	Pachati
Vayu	Apakarshayati
Kleda	Saidhilya Aapadayathi
Sneha	Mardavam Janayati

Pancha Mahabhuta And Bhutagni

1. They are of 5 types,
2. Parthiva agni
3. Aapya agni
4. taijasa agni,
5. Vaayaveeya agni
6. Naabhasa or akasheeya agni

The Bhutagni literally means the fire which is located within each of the Mahabhutas. In the process of digestion and metabolism, the

food passes through three levels of action of agni. At first it is acted upon by jatharagni for gross digestion. Then it is acted upon by bhutagni. At this level the agni component of each mahabhuta carries out selective digestion process of their respective component of food. The parthiva agni digests and metabolizes the Prithvi component of ingested food. Further the body constituents are formed by selective process of dhatvagni. [Cha.Chi 14-12/15] Body is formed of pancha mahabhuta and so is food. When food is ingested, the relevant mahabhuta and body component is increased [Su.Su.46/526].

Pharmacological Aspect

Substances are born from the combination of prithvi, ap ,teja, vayu and akasa. That which predominant among these becomes the cause for their classification such as parthiva, apya, taijasa, vayaviya, akasiya. [Su.Su.41/6-9].

According to Ashtanga Hridaya, dravya is composed of five basic elements. It has kshma –prithvi, as substratum, it take origin from ambu, agni, pavana and nabhas with their intimate and inseparable combination. its identification is decided by the predominance of particular element in it. [AH.SU.11/1,2]

Dravya bheda	Guna	Karma
Parthiva	स्थूल, सान्द्र, मन्द, स्थिर, गुरु, कठिनं, गन्धबहुलमीत्क-षायं प्रायशो मधुर	स्थैर्य, बल, गौरव, सङ्घातोपचयकरं विशेषतश्चाधोगतिस्वभाव
Aapya	शीत, स्तिमित, स्निग्ध, मन्द, गुरु, सर, सान्द्र, मृदु, पिच्छिलं रसबहुलमीषत्कषायाम्ललवणं मधुररसप्राय	श्लेहनह्लादन, क्लेदनबन्धन, विथन्दनकर
Taijasa	उष्ण, तीक्ष्ण, सूक्ष्म, रूक्ष, खर, लघु, विशदं रूपबहुल - मीषदम्ललवणं कटुकरसप्रायं विशेषतश्चोर्ध्वगतिस्वभाव	दहन, पचन, दारण, तापन, प्रकाशनप्रभावरणकर
Vayavya	सूक्ष्म, रूक्ष, खर, शिशिर, लघु, विशदं स्पर्शबहुलमीषत्किक्तं विशेषतः कषाय	शयलाघवग्लपनविरूक्षण विचारणकर
Akaseeya	श्लक्ष्णसूक्ष्ममृदुव्यवायिविशदविविक्तमव्यक्तरसं शब्दबहुल	तन्मादवशौषिर्यलाघवकर

Apart from the therapeutic uses mentioned above, the medicines having dominance of specific mahabhuta are administered in therapeutic procedures. This corresponds to relevant properties

and effect of mahabhuta .that which is predominant among these becomes the cause for their classification.

Panchabhoutikatwa of Shadrasa

Rasa	Mahabhuta
Madhura	Prithvi + Jala
Amla	Prithvi + Thejas
Lavana	Jala + Tejas
Tikta	Vayu + Akasa
Katu	Vayu + Tejas
Kashaya	Vayu + Prithvi

According to Brihatrayees each rasa is constituted by all the pancha mahabhutas but two of them are predominant. Neither Susrutacharya nor Ashtanga hridayakara says whether these two predominant mahabhutas are equal or unequal when compared with each other. Though Charakacharya and Sangrahaakara says that the main two bhutas unequal(oonathirekena) but did not say which one of the two is more predominant and which one is less predominant.

Even though the rasas are essentially constituted by the five bhutas(elements), the manifestation of certain bhutas in predominance during their origin results in the diversity. Purusha originates from the food he consumes. The dominance of a particular taste in the diet influences the creation of specific elemental components within the body. These rasas are solely responsible for dosha prakopa and manifestation of disease if used in improper way or by use of apathya.

Pancha Mahabhuta & Veerya

Regarding virya, Acharya Susruta presented a unique view on the relation of ashta viryas and mahabhuta [Su Su 41]

Vaisadyam	Pritvi, Vayu
Teekshna, Ushna	Agni
Seeta, Pichila	Jala
Sneha	Prithvi, Ambu
Mrdutvam	Jala
Roukshyam	Vayu

Just like rasas these veeryas are accountable for dosha prakopa and manifestation of disease if they are used in improper way or by use of apathyakara aahara. Ultimately wise vaidya must know the panchabhautika composition of dravyas to successfully treat the patient.

Samskara/ Biotransmission

It is known that *nasthi dravyam anoushadham* if administered in appropriate manner

योगादपि विषं तीक्ष्णमुत्तमं भेषजं भवेत्।

भेषजं चापि दुर्युक्तं तीक्ष्णं सम्पद्यते विषम् ॥ १२६॥ cha su 1/126

On the basis of thorough knowledge and understanding of Pancha mahabhuta siddhanta one can take an account of the causative factors for the imbalance of doshas and thereby find out the solution for the treatment. The Rasa, Guna and Karma of any dravya can be altered by performing appropriate Samskaar on dravyas if the drug requires some modifications according to disease, kaala etc, for example Ardraka (ginger) is soaked in lime water and dried in sunlight then its Jala Mahabhuta dominance gets decreased and Agni Mahabhuta dominance is increased comparatively, so that Ardraka having Guru Guna is converted into Sunthi having Laghu Guna.

So by samskaras mentioned in classics & understanding the logic of pancabhautika alteration behind it vaidya can use the available dravyas as per need. This Gunantaradhana is considered as biotransformation.

Panchamahabhutha in Chikitsa

Discussing the applicability of Pancha mahabhuta in chikitsa, the dual aspect of chikitsa ie, santarpana and apatarpana itself reveals the pivotal role of mahabhuta.

Santarpana – brmhana, snehana, swedana	Prithvi jala
Apatarpana- langhana, rukshana, stambana	Akasa vayu agni

According to Susruta, the following aushadha karmas is having mahabhuta predominance

Akasa	Samsamana
-------	-----------

Vayu	Sangrahika (since it is shoshana)
Agni	Deepana
Vayu and agni	Lekhana
Prithvi and jala	Brmhana

Pancha Mahabhuta & Triguna

Acharya susruta has mentioned the predominance of triguna in each mahabhuta.

तत्र सत्त्वबहुलमाकाशं, रजोबहुलो वायुः, सत्त्वरजोबहुलोऽग्निः, सत्त्वतमोबहुला आपः,
तमोबहुला पृथिवीति |(SU SHA 1/27)

Satva pariksha is the diagnostic method to evaluate the manobala of the patient. Hence by the assessment of the type and level of satva a vaidya can determine the method of treatment according to satva pariksha.

Pancha Mahabhuta and Tridosha

In Ayurveda the panchamahaboota siddhanta is adopted in a practical way . naturally it become highly essential in the context of application that the theory should be modified. These modified theories are very essential to keep the identity of a science and hence it is a pratitantra Siddhanta. Tridosha siddhanta is one among such theories which explain the functional constitution of body. Tridoshas are the innate forms of pancha mahabhuta . वाय्वाकाशधातुभ्यां वायुः । आग्नेयं पित्तम् । अम्भःपृथिवीभ्यां श्लेष्मा ॥ २॥ AS SU 20/2

Based on this composition, mahabhuta play vital role in determining basic constitution (prakriti) of human being. [Cha. Sa.VI.8/95]

This principle is applied in therapeutics, In case of decrease in vatadosha in body, the regimen which increase vayu and akasha mahahuta is prescribed. Accordingly the regimens which increase corresponding doshas are prescribed.

Application of Panchmahabhuta In Disease Management

Imbalance /variation in the panchabhoutika constitution may lead to various diseases. Then the medicine having opposite panchabhoutika constitution are administered to restore equilibrium in the body. For example, in the conventional type of jwara the aama

which is caused due to the undigested food leads to rasa dhatu dusti. From which we can understand that the digestion and metabolism has slowed down. So we can infer that the Prithvi and jala mahabhuta has increased leading to manifestation of jwara. So the main treatment principle for jwara is langhana, swedana, pachana, and tikta rasa which results in the increase in the agni, vayu and akasha mahabhuta. Which helps in the jwaraprasamana.

As another example, In kushta roga one of the main nidana is atisevana of viruddhahara which causes the increase of prthvi and jala guna in the body leading to srotavarodha and also avarana of agni which will result in ajirna and circulation of apakva ahara rasa all over the body and eventually results in mandalotpatti. Considering the samprapti the condition can be managed with Teja, Vayu and Akasha mahabhuta dominated Dravyas.

Pancha Mahabhuta in Shodhana Therapy

Susruta acharya stated that Virechana dravyas are always having Prithvi and Jala mahabhuta dominancy since Prithvi and Jala mahabhuta are having Guru gunas and According to Vaisheshika philosophy, adhopatana is the prime property of guru guna. As Agni and Vayu mahabhutas are urdhwagami and having laghu gunas therefore dravya with dominancy of these two mahabhutas helps in vaman karma.

This is the influence of mahabhutas for movement of dosha towards koshta.

Dosha Movement	Mahabhuta
Vridhhi	Prithvi &Jala
Abhishyandana	Jala & Teja
Paaka(Digestion)	Teja
Srotomugha Visodhana	Akasha
Vayu Nigraha	Vayu

Classification of Marma Based on Pancha Mahabhuta Predominance

The marma or vital points/organs in body are classified in five categories on the basis of their harmful effect on body. The harmful effect depends upon their fundamental composition.

Types of Marma	Panchabhctic Constitution
Sadyapranahara (that which cause immediate death)	Agni
Kaalantarapranahara (that which cause death after some time)	Jala, Agni
Vishalyaghna (that which cause death by removal of foreign body)	Vayu
Vaikalyakara (that which cause disability or deformities)	Jala
Rujakara (that which cause pain)	Agni, Vayu

Pancha Mahabhuta In Prognosis

In indriya sthaana acharya has mentioned five types of cchaya according to the Pancha mahabhuta predominance.

Cchaya	Lakshana
Akasi	Nirmala nila sasneha saprabha
Vayavi	Ruksha syava aruna hathaprabha
Agneyi	Visydharaktaavarna deepthabha darsanapriya
Ambhasi	Sudha like vaidurya snighdha
Parthivi	Sthira snigda khana slakshna syama sweta

Among these vayavi is inauspicious and causes death or other serious troubles and pains while others are indicative of pleasure or happiness. Acharya also says about saptha prabha which are tejo mahobhutha predominant. Among them which are ruksha malina and samkshiptha indicates asubha or indicates imminent death

Pancha Mahabhuta And Marana

शरीरं हि गते तस्मिञ् शून्यागारमचेतनम्।

पञ्चभूतावशेषत्वात् पञ्चत्वंगतमुच्यते ॥ Ch Sha 1/74

The panmahabhuta revolves around the normal functioning of the body, (physiological), pathological and action of drug in various part of the body(pharmacokinetics).

During the time of death, When the soul, with all its associates (indriyas, manas and four subtle mahabhutas) departs, the body becomes vacant and is deprived of consciousness. Only the five mahabhutas remain. So, a dead body is said to have attained the state of five mahabhutas (panchtatva). At last at the time of death all these 5 elements are dissolved into their respective elements of nature, so that it can balance the cycle of nature.

Conclusion

Pancha mahabhuta siddhanta is a core framework for comprehending the structure of both the world and the human body, providing vital insights into health, wellness, and the interconnectedness of all living beings. Human body is Panchabhautika and the food we eat is also Panchabhautika when the food undergoes digestion with the help of Jatharagni. Parthiva properties of food nourish the Parthiva parts of the body. In this manner, symmetrical properties of Mahabhutas give nutrition to corresponding symmetrical organs of the body. In fact, every Dravya in this universe has its Pancha mahabhuta composition irrespective of whether they are Chetana or Achetana.

References

- Dr. Sreekumar. Ashtanga Hridaya 3rd ed. Kerala, Mannuthy: Harisree Hospital Publication Department; 2011.
- Chakrapani. Charaka Samhita, 1st ed. Varanasi, India: Chaukhambha Vishvabharati; 2017.
- Dr. Tewari. Charaka Samhita, 1st ed. Varanasi, India: Chaukhambha Vishvabharati; 2017.
- Sharma PV. Susruta Samhita, Varanasi, Chaukhambha Vishvabharati: 2022.
- Ashtanga Hridayam Shareera sthana 10th ed. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Orientalia; 2011
- Annambhatta, jha VN. Tarkasangraha of Annambhatta; English translation with notes. Ernakulam: Chinmaya International Foundation Shodha Sansthan; 2010

KIRANĀVALĪ

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

The New Trivandrum Sanskrit Series Vol. XVI. Book I-IV

January - December 2024

ISSN 0975-4067

Printed and published by: Dr.C.S.Sasikumar, Secretary, Sanskrit Research Foundation, Thiruvananthapuram, for Sanskrit Research Foundation,